

Agent-based simulation of normal mass events egress using groups behavioral modeling

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Abstract

Public mass events require thorough planning on allocating resources such as paramedics, police officers, urban cleaning teams, and their equipment (ambulances, patrol cars, garbage collection trucks, and other urban cleaning vehicles). That planning requires the participation a myriad of stakeholders.

Our main objective is to facilitate participatory discussions on various scenarios, regarding the scheduling of mentioned resources. For each scenario, we need to know how long it takes the normal (non-urgent) egress process for the vast majority of participants. That is when some resources are released (police and paramedics) and urban cleaning teams start working. Since participants in mass events usually gather in social groups, we also want to assess how their dynamics affect the overall egress process.

Using the agent-based GAMA platform, we implemented a spatially explicit simulation model upon an extension of the Social Force Model (SFM) that considers group behavior. We present the ODD protocol describing that model, thus improving its clarity and facilitating its deployment and experimental replication.

We present the outcome of simulations with different scenarios, in terms of group sizes and crowd densities, upon a digital twin of a historic square in Lisbon, Portugal, where mass events often take place. We analyzed model performance when the number of agents (the participants' surrogates) increases, to assess the feasibility of using our approach in a participatory approach with stakeholders responsible for resources management.

The behavior of groups of agents, visualized through the proposed diachronic plots, evidenced real-life phenomena, such as the persistence of group cohesion and repulsion interactions (both with architectural obstacles and other agents). Nevertheless, simulations have not shown a significant impact due to average group sizes in egress times, for the studied scenarios. Both the values of egress periods and group behaviors were considered plausible by an expert panel. Model performance degradation may hamper the usage of this model/platform for participatory meetings due to the incurred delay in obtaining results. In future work, to mitigate this problem, we plan to explore parallelization strategies for agent-based simulation, such as the use of GPUs.

Keywords: agent-based modeling, pedestrians simulation, egress, evacuation, social force model, groups, ODD protocol

1. Introduction

Cities have integrated into their tourism development strategies the realization of crowded pedestrian events in public spaces, such as music festivals, fireworks, and video mapping shows. Other public events such as political rallies, protests, celebrations, or commemorations can attract an immense number of visitors.

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Choosing adequate public space for each of these events requires knowing the expected number of visitors, acoustic conditions, spatial context, and accessibility. It is also necessary to undertake risk analysis based on the carrying capacity and egress time from the public space hosting the event. The safety of urban public space events depends on a wide set of factors, such as the scope of the event, the profile of the expected visitors, and the geometry of the space. For instance, a protest of senior citizens over the degradation of their pensions would have different risk factors when compared to a concert for younger crowds. A rally for a tolerance-preaching political party would not be as risky as an extremist radical party rally. A quick event would probably not potentiate as much damage as a long-duration event. In case of the appearance of order-disrupting situations, such as natural disasters, explosions, or terrorist attacks, the geometry of the public space must allow for quick and efficient evacuation, in order to avoid or keep casualties to a minimum.

In this paper, we only consider the most recurrent situation in which events end, with a non-urgent outflow of the public space in which they took place. Nevertheless, for the success of these "normal" events, adequate planning is required to allow dealing with potential health emergencies that on average will occur due to a large number of participants, and guarantee public safety during the event and, after it, ensure that the venue is kept clean for later use by the city's inhabitants and visitors. That requires the scheduling of resources such as paramedics, police officers, urban cleaning teams, and their equipment (ambulances, patrol cars, garbage collection trucks, and other urban cleaning vehicles).

In this context, a simulation model can be an effective planning tool for stakeholders to explore the complex system of event maneuvering by allowing the testing of multiple scenarios without requiring empirical observation. Models can also be applied in approaches for the participatory description of complex systems, e.g., the Companion Modeling approach [4], which allows for the continuous improvement via the co-creation of conceptual models by stakeholders with possibly different views.

To obtain realistic and meaningful results, the model should describe a variety of possible microscopic phenomena of the different partaking agents. One such phenomenon is that these events are usually attended by social groups of pedestrians who walk together (e.g., friends, and family). The interactions within each group and among members of different groups have an impact on the crowd behavior dynamics [15], which could also affect the efficiency of event egress. Although this is an important aspect of pedestrian dynamics, it has been often neglected in pedestrian flow models [3].

Through the use of OpenStreetMap (OSM) ¹ geographical data and the GAMA modeling and simulation development environment ², we developed an agent-based model (ABM) to simulate non-urgent egress dynamics of pedestrians from mass events in public open spaces, implementing an existing validated group behavior model based on the extended Social Force Model (SFM), proposed in [15]. Using the presented model, we perform simulated experiments to assess the effects of average social group size on egress times. A performance analysis is performed to assess the feasibility of the usage of this model for participatory planning among stakeholders.

This paper is organized as follows: in section 2 we recap the SFM and its extension to support group dynamics behavior; then, in section 3, we review some of the most relevant related works; in section 4 we present our agent-based model, covering the simulation platform, the description of how the geographical location was mapped in the simulation environment, how agents behavior was modeled and some additional model assumptions; on section 5 we describe the used simulation scenarios and present the obtained simulation results and discuss them on section 6; finally, on section 7, we provide some conclusions and outline the future work.

2. Background

The classic SFM, presented by Helbing et al. [7], is a microscopic mathematical model that represents pedestrian dynamics and interactions, based on the concept of *social forces*, presented by Lewin [12] as psychological forces from the environment and other pedestrians, which collectively act upon the decision-making of the movement of pedestrians, resulting in the manifestation of a decided velocity.

¹<https://www.openstreetmap.org/about>

²<https://gama-platform.org/>

In the classic SFM from Helbing et al., there are 3 main terms regarding the assessment of the driving force of the actual velocity of a pedestrian: (i) The force towards the desired velocity, dependent on the desired walking speed and the directions towards the destination, (ii) the repulsive forces from other pedestrians and obstacles (e.g., borders, walls, statues), to avoid and keep distance from them and (iii) the attractive forces from other possible sources (e.g., a shopping window on a way to a destination). The SFM has been widely used in pedestrian behavior models and simulations, with some modifications (e.g. the attractive forces are often neglected) and improvements to consider additional phenomena such as panic behavior [6].

While the classic SFM does not implement group behavior, there are some relevant proposals for modeling social group behavior in pedestrian dynamics, based on SFM. Moussaïd et. al [15] presented extensions to the classic SFM, to represent inter-group and intra-group interactions of repulsion and attraction. Those authors extended the classic SFM with the following components: (i) intra-group interactions based on gaze, (ii) the attraction of group members to the group's center of mass, responsible for group cohesion, and (iii) the repulsion interactions between group members to avoid collisions.

In [8], the authors present a more advanced extension to the previously referred group SFM. This model adds the following components: (i) the repulsion forces between groups and (ii) subgroup coordination forces.

3. Related Work

Many pedestrian flow models have been developed, using multiple modeling types (e.g., ABM, Cellular Automata (CA)), some applied to evacuation scenarios, some used for the study of isolated pedestrian dynamics. Since we used an ABM with groups behavior in the context of evacuation simulation, that will be the scope of this brief literature review, that will be presented in chronological order. The inclusion criteria for selected papers, besides topic coverage, were:

- Published in a journal
- Indexed by Scopus ³, one of the most important scientific indexing databases [19]
- Written in English
- Community recognition (at least an average of 4 citations per year since publishing, according to Google Scholar ⁴)

Qiu et al. [16] presented an ABM based on the Reynold's Boids algorithm to simulate group behavior in crowd evacuation, assessing the influence of group size, intra-group structure, and inter-group relationships. The authors concluded that the factors in study are important in crowd evacuation.

Lemercier et al [11] proposed an RVO2-based ABM to assess the influence of the perceptions of pedestrians on their attitudes in a crowd evacuation. RVO2 is a collision avoidance model proposed in [22]. By simulating leader-follower behavior, grouping, or not grouping, the authors concluded that a more realistic crowd behavior can be modeled by combining these different behaviors.

Ma et al [14] proposed an extension of the classic SFM to simulate leader-follower behavior in crowd evacuation, incorporating the visibility range of the area. The authors concluded that the impact of leadership on evacuation time depends on the range of visibility of the area and crowd size.

Li et al [13] also presented an extension to the classic SFM by Helbing and Mólnar for crowd evacuation, incorporating social groups and leader-follower behavior. Based on the results, the authors concluded group behavior causes more efficiency in egress than the classic SFM model.

Turgut et al. [21] presented an extended SFM model with 2 types of group behavior: leader-centered and group-centered behavior. Through the analysis of simulations in evacuation scenarios, the authors concluded that in (i) small groups, evacuation time is lower in leader-centered than in group-centered behavior (ii) the

³<https://www.scopus.com/>

⁴<https://scholar.google.com/>

Table 1: Related work summary

Reference	Non-urgent egress	Real life scenario simulation	ABM Platform/Library
[16]	No	No	OpenSteer
[11]	No	No	RVO2
[14]	No	No	-
[13]	No	No	Multiple platforms
[21]	No	No	AnyLogic
Our model	Yes	Yes	GAMA

increase of leaders reduced evacuation time and (iii) with multiple exits, group-centered behavior resulted in less evacuation time and better exit choice balancing than leader-centered behavior.

Most of these studies focus on leader-following or herding effect of emergency evacuation, and not groups derived from social ties in non-urgent egress. These studies also do not apply simulations in large scale, real environments. Table 1 shows a summary of the selected related studies and classifications attributes, in comparison with the one presented here. The attributes are explained as follows:

- Reference: The source of the study;
- Non-urgent egress: Indicates whether the model describes evacuation in non-urgent scenarios;
- Real life scenario simulation: The model is applied to a scenario representing real-life (e.g., simulation of pedestrian flows in a digital representation of a concrete real space);
- ABM Platform/ Library: The platform/tool/library used to implement and simulate models.

4. Agent-based model

This section presents an abbreviated version of our proposed ABM. We used the Overview, Design concepts, and Details (ODD) protocol, which was proposed as a standardized format for providing a consistent, logical, and readable account of the structure and dynamics of ABMs [5]. Many examples based on ODD can be found online at the CoMSES Model Library⁵, a digital repository that enforces reproducibility, and reuse of ABMs [10].

Our aim was to simulate the non-urgent egress of visitors from mass gathering events in public open spaces, namely, squares or plazas, in order to understand how the different built environments of the open spaces, crowd density, exit choosing scenarios and group behavior affect the egress times of the event visitors. In this paper, we solely focus on the effects of group behavior.

We used an OSM fragment representing the chosen open urban space, upon which we added rectangular geometry data for representing the exit gates. The leaving pedestrians were modeled as autonomous agents who interact with each other and the environment in order to progress towards the exit gates, simulating crowd maneuvering. The simulations of the model in various scenarios were run on a remote Virtual Machine (VM), generating data files and simulation snapshots for the analysis of the results. The main outcome variables obtained from simulations of the model were (i) the remaining pedestrians at each simulation cycle, from which is derived the total egress time of 90% of the attendees, and (ii) the total collisions detected in each cycle. A collision was considered to occur when 2 pedestrians from different groups were less than 0.5 meters apart.

⁵<https://www.comses.net/codebases/>

4.1. Simulation platform

The presented model was implemented using version 1.8.1 of the *GAMA platform* ⁶. It is an Eclipse-based ⁷ Integrated Development Environment (IDE) for spatially explicit, agent-based and agent-oriented modeling and simulation [20]. The platform is designed to develop and run complex, large-scale models, with a wide support for integrating and visualizing geographic information systems (GIS) data. It also provides a headless mode, allowing to run simulations in dedicated servers without the overhead of a user interface.

4.2. Environment

The model environment is composed by the buildings that delimit the open space, and the exit geometries, which are modeled as polygons that cover the entrances to the exiting streets, bordering the open space polygon.

We used QGIS 3.16 LTS ⁸ to manually model the exit geometries and open space limits polygon, and to download and process OSM building geometry data to model the built environment of the public open spaces.

4.3. Agent modeling

In this model, the behavior of the pedestrian agents is orchestrated by the Model agent (an observer agent), in order to try to harness the experimental usage of concurrent processing of agents, present in this version of the GAMA platform, to mimic their autonomy. This agent is also responsible for calculating the result statistics (i.e., average pedestrian speed, pedestrian egress, collisions).

The active agents in the model are the pedestrians who egress from the open space, the Model agent, and the Group agents.

The pedestrian agents walk toward the chosen exit using a simplified (due to performance concerns for massive simulations) implementation of the extended SFM for group behavior presented in [15], based on the model of Helbing et. al. [7]. For every simulation cycle, each pedestrian agent evaluates the repulsive social forces other pedestrians and obstacles act upon them, and attractive forces representing group cohesion. Group agents store references of their members to improve efficiency in the calculation of the intra-group forces and calculate the group's centroid (center of mass), which is required both for path calculation and in visualization. Building geometries are also considered agents but do not have behavior, serving as obstacles for the SFM submodel.

Group agents:

The number of groups is calculated from the total number of pedestrians and group size. At the beginning of a simulation, for each group, a group center location is randomly created to guarantee a uniform distribution across the environment area. The pedestrians are then spawned at a set distance to the center of their respective groups. At each cycle, a group agent behaves as follows:

1. The group agent checks if a group member has left the simulation. If that happens, it is removed from group's list of members.
2. The agent calculates the group's centroid based on the current position of all its current members.
3. If there are no members left, the group agent is removed from the simulation.

Pedestrian agents:

When the pedestrians spawn, they are assigned to their groups, and all members of a group are randomly placed at a location within 2 meters from the center of their group. Then, every group chooses an exit, randomly distributed by the weight of the exit width (i.e., a wider exit is more likely to be chosen than a narrow one), where every of its members wants to reach. At each cycle, the pedestrian agents follow the following steps:

⁶<https://gama-platform.org/>

⁷<https://www.eclipse.org/>

⁸<https://qgis.org/en/site/>

(a) Aerial view of the real twin (Google Maps)

(b) Digital twin on GAMA with 2600 pedestrian agents

Figure 1: Simulation environment (Lisbon town-hall square)

1. For each member of the agent's group, it calculates the repulsive forces exerted by the member and the attraction forces to the group's centroid (obtained from the group agent), using the respective equations from [15], accumulating them in the total sum of forces;
2. For each neighbor pedestrian within the defined distance from the agent, which is not part of its social group, it calculates the repulsive forces exerted by pedestrians within a defined distance using the classic SFM motion equation [7], adding them to the total sum of forces.
3. The agent displaces according to the speed obtained for the final sum of forces.
4. If the agent reaches its chosen exit geometry, it is removed from the simulation. Else, returns to step 1.

5. Simulation Scenarios

The following simulation scenarios are set on a digital twin of the Praça do Município square, Lisbon, which has been a host of numerous mass events (e.g., football celebrations, political events) and allows for simulations with medium to high agents density with an acceptable total pedestrian count. The environment was modeled with OSM data. Figure 1a shows the aerial view of the modeled open space, and Figure 1b shows a snapshot of its simulated digital twin, populated with pedestrian agents. There are two main scenarios of crowd density

The number of pedestrians in the simulations for the main scenarios were based on the total area of the open public space ($5200 m^2$) and in the defined areas per pedestrian of $2 m^2$ and $0.5 m^2$ per pedestrian, based on the highway pedestrian usage levels of service for moving pedestrians D and F (LOS), respectively, defined in the Highway Capacity Manual [18]. The total approximated values of pedestrians in each simulation set was therefore 2600 and 10400 pedestrians.

To assess the group behavior effects on egress times for each crowd density scenario, a subset of scenarios was defined. In the base scenario, there were no groups of pedestrians (i.e. the group size was set to 1), used as a control scenario. In the other scenarios, the number of elements of a group (N) varied from 2 to 7 pedestrians. The defined step for each simulation cycle was 0.1 seconds. Simulations ended when the percentage of remaining pedestrians in the open space reached 10% of the initial value. In other words, simulations elapsed to allow egress of 90% of the visitors.

The model parameters defined for these simulations and set values are depicted in Table 2. The parameters for the classic SFM were set based on the simulations made in the original study [7]. The parameters for the group SFM component were chosen based on multiple simulations, until group behavior provided more realism, through discussion followed by group consensus among the authors. This *expert-panel* approach

Table 2: Model parameters and their assigned values for the simulations

Parameter	Description	Value
V0	Desired walking speed of a pedestrian	1.3 (m/s)
A_ped	The pedestrian repulsion strength parameter of the classic SFM	2.1
D_ped	The pedestrian range of repulsive forces parameter of the classic SFM	0.3 (meters)
A_obs	The obstacle repulsion strength parameter of the classic SFM	10
D_obs	The obstacle range of repulsive forces parameter of the classic SFM	0.2
ped_influence_radius	The range within which a pedestrian exerts social forces	1 (meters)
obs_influence_radius	The range within which an obstacle exerts social forces	5 (meters)
Tr	The relaxation parameter of the classic SFM	0.5 (seconds)
shoulder_length	The shoulder width of the pedestrians	0.45 (meters)
B_group_attr	The intra-group attraction strength parameter of the extended group SFM	10
B_group_rep	The intra-group repulsion strength parameter of the extended group SFM	1
group_rep_threshold	The range within which group members exert repulsive forces	0.65 (meters)
group_attr_threshold	The distance from group center from which attractive forces occur	$(N-1)/2$

was required due to the lack of empirical studies for high-density group behavior in mass events. Further calibration of these parameters should be done in future work.

As an output of each simulation, GAMA provides: (i) graphical snapshots of the positioning of agents throughout time and (ii) a set of CSV files with the outcome variables (remaining pedestrians), where each line corresponds to 1 simulated second.

6. Results and discussion

6.1. Collected data analysis

In Figure 2, we can observe a close up snapshot (extract) of a simulation scenario with groups of 4 elements, showing the paths of a single group throughout several simulation cycles. The dotted lines below each colored agent (purple triangles) represent the individual paths, where each dot represents a position in a previous cycle, and the black line represents the path of the group’s centroid. These paths show an avoidance pattern to other pedestrians / groups, as we can observe accentuated speed changes (value and direction) and a following cohesion pattern, showing the model’s ability to describe these behaviors.

For an initial model stochasticity test, a set of 10 simulations for the scenario of groups of 4 elements ($N=4$) was performed. In Figure 3 is depicted a graph showing the egress patterns across the 10 simulations of the previously presented scenario. The variations of egress time show slight oscillation, which can be explained by the random nature of exit choice, which has an impact on overall egress performance (orderly exit will have a greater performance than a chaotic exit). This suggests that slight oscillations in the following results for different group sizes should be taken as an effect of randomness.

Figures 4a and 4b show the patterns of egress for crowd counts of approximately 2600 and 10400 pedestrians, respectively, for one simulation and for each group size scenario. The egress evolution follows a similar pattern in both crowd densities, but, due to the significant differences in pedestrian count, which increase collisions and the chance of bottlenecks, the egress times are longer for 10400 pedestrians.

The egress evolution pattern variations are similar to those observed in the stochasticity test scenario, hinting that group behavior does not have a meaningful effect on egress times in the present crowd densities and built environment scenario.

In Figure 5, we can observe the egress times obtained in the simulations, by group size and crowd density scenario, allowing to compare the effects of group size in egress times in each crowd density scenario. The data suggests there is not a significant impact of the implemented group behavior in non-urgent egress in these scenarios, as we cannot find a pattern connecting group size with the egress time, and the fluctuations between the results of different group sizes are not meaningful enough, possibly being caused by stochasticity. It is possible the group behavior has a more meaningful impact in different built environments, more extreme crowd densities and different parameter values for the group extended SFM model. Further simulations in these scenarios and parameter calibration should be performed to test the hypothesis.

Figure 2: Snapshot of simulation with groups of 4 pedestrians, showing the paths of one group upon a series of cycles

Figure 3: Stochasticity effect on egress size ($N=4$, 2600 pedestrians)

(a) Egress evolution pattern by group size (2600 pedestrians)

(b) Egress evolution pattern by group size (10400 pedestrians)

Figure 4: Simulation results

Figure 5: Graph of the resulting egress times by group size and crowd density scenario

6.2. Threats to the validity

Models are, by definition, abstractions, and therefore do not convey all the details of reality. In our ABM we considered some simplifying assumptions that may be considered as potential internal validity threats. We address each one separately.

All area without buildings inside the bounding polygon is considered usable area. In urban open space mass events, roads are often blocked to vehicles, only allowing pedestrians or special vehicles traffic (e.g., ambulances, police cars, event staff vehicles). In our example we omitted the latter (that can be seen to the right in Figure 1a), as well as the central statue and the round kiosk bar in one of the corners of the town-hall square.

In urgent egress situations, individuals in panic often adopt an herd mentality and choose the closest exit to evacuate as quickly as possible [24]. In the, fortunately much more recurring, non-urgent egress situations, it is not trivial to predict where the crowds go, as it will depend on their final destination, means of transportation, and even on the time of the day when the event occurred. In the absence of empirical data, the best alternative we have devised was assigning the choice of exit gate for each group based on a weighted randomization (random quotas) decision, where the weights were the exit widths. In other words, wider exits were more likely to be assigned than narrow ones. On average, the same number of pedestrians is expected to flow out per unit of exit width.

To study the influence of group size, we blocked group size variability from scenario to scenario. In other words, for each simulation scenario group sizes were homogeneous. Non-homogeneous groupings should be analyzed as well, but their actual distribution requires further research on related work. Our own empirical evidence is that the size of groups can vary widely and also be dependent on the type of event. For instance an event targeted at families is likely to have an average group size smaller than an event for youngsters, like a hard-rock concert.

Finally, pedestrian flow beyond the exits is not considered, being assumed as non restricting to egress flow. Any constraints to the flow of pedestrians beyond the exits would influence the egress rates, but that is unlikely in most real case scenarios.

6.3. Simulation performance

All simulations were deployed and run on a VM created on top of *OpenStack*⁹, a free, open standard cloud computing platform used by INCD to provide computing and storage services to the Portuguese scientific community¹⁰. The machine runs as operating system the Linux distribution Ubuntu 20-04, having 8 virtual CPU and 128 GB of RAM, allowing the running of a suitable number of parallel simulations with decent memory allocated to each.

To test how execution time varies with the number of pedestrian agents, we measured the real-life time (in milliseconds) of the first cycle (after the initial model loading time) of isolated simulations (i.e., each simulation was running without other simultaneous simulations) with the same general scenario, but with different agent population sizes and maintaining a group size of 4. In each simulation, the agent population size was set with a value ranged from 1000 to 20000 agents in increments of 1000 (except between 15000 and 20000) Using curve-fitting techniques and tools to extract the collision patterns, we obtained the following approximated equation for relation between cycle time and agent number in this scenario:

$$T_{cycle} = 0.000037N_{agents}^{2.2} \quad (1)$$

Figure 6 depicts a graph with the measurements collected from these simulations, and the estimated equation fitted for the data. We can observe a close fitting with the available data points, suggesting a near-quadratic evolution of the execution time in a single cycle.

Using a composition between the cycle time equation and pedestrian agent count at each time period (10 cycles) for example simulations, we can estimate its isolated execution time. From the data of a simulation

⁹<https://www.openstack.org/>

¹⁰<https://www.incd.pt/?p=servicos/cloud&lang=en>

Figure 6: Relation between pedestrian agent count and simulation cycle time

with 4 group members and 2600 pedestrians, the estimated execution time is 9 minutes and 25 seconds. For 10000 pedestrians, a total of 8 hours, 13 minutes and 43 seconds is estimated.

The total execution time of a simulation may evolve more-than-quadratically with agent count, due to the possibility that a simulation with a massive number of agents needs considerably more cycles, and each cycle takes more time to complete, as suggested by the approximated curve, generating a compounding effect. For massive simulations, the execution time would be impractically long for stakeholder participation.

The simulation speed is also shown to be affected by group size. The execution time of simulations increased with the decrease of group size, despite the collision count and egress times being similar. This is possibly due to fact that when the groups are shorter, the number of groups is higher when maintaining the total crowd count. This would lead to more calculations from the group agents.

An attempt to harness the experimental parallelization feature of the GAMA platform was done for parallel SFM computing for each agent, but it was not enough to increase performance.

7. Conclusions and Future Work

The research presented in this paper is a continuation of our previous work [2], analyzing the egress time for multiple scenarios of crowd density in the open spaces using a derived model for egress flow rates in exits, from the *Society of Fire Protection Engineers (SFPE) Handbook* [9], and [1], where the initial version of the simulation model is introduced, without the implementation of group behavior.

In this article, we presented an ABM to simulate the non-urgent egress of pedestrians from mass events, considering group behavior. Using the GAMA platform, we simulated the egress of 2600 and 10400 pedestrians from the Praça do Município square in Lisbon, defining different group size scenarios. The full description of our ABM model is the ODD protocol that can be found in Appendix A. The source code for our GAMA implementation can be found in GitHub ¹¹.

According to the analysis of the data obtained from the simulations, the group behavior seems to not affect egress for the given scenarios. Scenarios of different built environments, extreme crowd densities and exit choice behaviors should be done, as well as possibly improving group behavior implementation.

¹¹https://github.com/duartealmeida/pedestrian_egress_abm

Since we aim at developing digital twinning models for extreme crowding situations, we need to generate simulations with a higher pedestrian density, allowing a more precise assessment of the social group behavior effect on non-urgent mass event egress. However, with the current setup, simulation time increases more-than-quadratically with the increase of the number of agents, making it unfeasible beyond a certain limit for real-time stakeholder participation. To mitigate this problem, we plan to explore algorithm efficiency and the usage of GPU-enhanced ABM tools such as *Flame GPU* [17] to increase concurrency in agent calculations, allowing us to simulate scenarios with a massive number of agents and lower execution time, possibly allowing real-time or faster-than-real-time visualization.

To improve model realism, therefore mitigating internal validity threats, we also plan to incorporate into the ABM model the more advanced group SFM presented in [8]. Still, observation and studies of mass crowd non-urgent egress conditions should be performed to allow calibration of model parameters and to detect additional macroscopic and microscopic behavior to be modeled in the agents.

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Appendix A. Model ODD protocol

Appendix A.1. Purpose and patterns

The purpose of the model is to simulate non-urgent egress of visitors from mass gathering events happening in real-life urban public open spaces (e.g., squares, plazas), evaluating the impact of different built environments, hypothetical exit choosing behaviors of the visitors, crowd density scenarios and number of individuals in a social group in the egress times, the main emergent phenomenon obtained from the model. The model should aid decision-makers to choose the appropriate public spaces for a specific event, and to timely deploy public utility teams (e.g., cleaning, emergency, security). The patterns we believe our model must be able to reproduce are the following:

- **Pattern 1: Relation between built environment layout and egress times.** The layout of the obstacles and exits, total space geometry, the total available exit width, as well as the shape of the open space should affect egress rates. E.g., a closed environment with a single small exit should lead to larger egress times than the same environment, but with more, wider exits.
- **Pattern 2: Relation between egress choosing behavior and egress times.** Chaotic exit choosing should lead to higher egress times, as a greater number of collisions between erratic pedestrians should overall reduce the egress rates. Whereas, an orderly behavior should minimize collisions, smoothing the flow of pedestrians towards the available exits.
- **Pattern 3: Relation between crowd density and egress times.** It is expected a significantly denser crowd egresses a built environment with less efficiency due to the increasing expected collisions between the pedestrians and bottlenecks at exits.
- **Pattern 4: Pedestrian collision avoidance** Pedestrians avoid bumping onto other pedestrians and other obstacles, maintaining a certain distance between them and altering their routes in order to avoid them. This pattern is based on the Social Force Model by Helbing et al. [7]
- **Pattern 5: Group cohesion.** Members of a social group maintain a spatial cohesion, i.e., maintain a certain proximity to each other. This pattern is based on group behavior studies [15, 8]

Patterns 1,2 and 3 are based on evacuation principles described in the *Society of Fire Protection Engineers (SFPE) Handbook* [9], which we believe can be observed in non-urgent egress as well.

Appendix A.2. Entities, state variables, and scales

Appendix A.2.1. Entities

There are 4 entity types partaking in this model: (i) the Model entity, (ii) environment entities, (iii) pedestrian agents and (iv) group agents.

The Model entity only serves as an orchestrator of the domain entities, controlling the behavior of most agents as if the agents were autonomous. The use of this entity was chosen to test the parallelization features of the GAMA Platform.

The environment entities are composed of the GIS polygonal representations of the buildings that surround and delimit the open space, as well as the buildings inside the space (e.g., statues, monuments), the usable area of each public open space, which is modeled as a polygon enclosed by the surrounding buildings or borders with bodies of water (e.g., river boundaries, coast), where pedestrians will randomly spawn, and the exit geometries (or targets), which are modeled as polygons that cover the entrances to the exiting streets, bordering the open space polygons.

The pedestrian agents represent the visitors of the event, who egress from it. The group agents represent the social groups in which the pedestrians are organized (e.g, a family, a group of friends).

These were the chosen entities, as the model is intended to assess the impact of the interactions between these entities have on egress times.

Appendix A.3. State variables

The environment entities are static and passive, and serve as limits or targets for the pedestrian agents. Thus, the only state variables of these entities are their geometry configurations. In Table A.3, the state variables of the remaining entities are presented.

Table A.3: Model state variables

Entity	Variable	Description	Possible Values	Units
Pedestrian	speedX	The X-axis component of the instantaneous speed	-	m/s
	speedY	The Y-axis component of the instantaneous speed	-	m/s
	heading	The instantaneous angle of direction	-	Degrees
	exit_target	The exit the pedestrian wants to reach	Environment entity (exit)	-
	location	The spatial location of the agent	Location point	-
Group	id	The identifier of the group	-	-
	members	The list of members of the group	List of pedestrians	-
	centroid	The center of mass of the group	Location point	-

Appendix A.4. Scale

This ABM represents both space and time. The space is two-dimensional and finite, and is represented in a continuous scale. The dimensions of the environment depend on the represented open space. The elementary unit of time represented in the model is 0.1 seconds, which is the value of the time step in a simulation cycle. The scales were chosen in a compromise between realism (the more continuous space and time are, the more realistic the model is) and simulation execution time.

Appendix A.5. Process overview and scheduling

The whole process and scheduling are fairly simple. In the start of a simulation, the model agent initializes the environment geometries, groups and pedestrians. After the spawn, at each simulation time step, the agents behave as follows:

1. The group agents execute the group submodel (in an undefined order), calculating their centroids and managing group member activity.
2. In an undefined order, the pedestrian agents execute the egress submodel, in which they move towards their chosen exits.
3. At each simulation second (10 steps), the model updates the output files with the number of remaining pedestrians in the simulation.

A simulation ends when the number of active pedestrians reaches 10% or less of the number of spawned pedestrians.

Appendix A.6. Design concepts

Appendix A.7. Basic principles

The model is set over the concept of pedestrians attending a mass gathering event, and leaving the venue after the end of the event, without urgency. It appears this particular system has not been yet addressed in the state of the art. Some studies and ABM have been developed addressing egress flow dynamics similar to the ones described in the model, but represent a much smaller scale (usually room-scale), and different contexts [23]. At the agent level, the interactions between the crowd members follow the established Social Force Model (SFM) first presented by Helbing et. al. [7], extended with social group behavior in [15]. The social force models represent repulsive and attractive forces that act upon the psychology of the pedestrians, dictating an actual velocity to be chosen by a pedestrian, in order to avoid obstacles/other pedestrians and reach the desired destination. The social group extension adds group cohesion forces, as pedestrians from a group want to be close to each other [15]. As opposed to scenarios of evacuation, where the chosen exit will

depend on multiple factors, such as panic states, distance to exit, etc., the egress in non-urgent scenarios will depend on the will of the pedestrians. Some may go to nearby bars, others may want to enter public transportation to return to their homes. This behavior is hard to predict due to a multitude of factors, and as such, the exit choice is modeled as a random process, weighted by the exit width. The choice is made as a group, as it is assumed all members of a group want to go to the same location.

The model tries to approximate reality by setting a continuous space, a fine-grained time scale, and the microscopic representation of all individual pedestrians.

Appendix A.8. Emergence

The main emergent phenomenon obtained from the model is the egress time. It represents the time that the pedestrians take to leave the open space, and it emerges from the interaction between the pedestrian agents, in form of social forces, and their spatial displacement towards the chosen exit. The model does not include imposed results.

Appendix A.9. Adaptation

The pedestrian agents adapt their desired velocity during each step according to the social forces acting upon them, which come from the other neighboring agents.

Appendix A.10. Objectives

The adaptation of the agents do not have clear decision-making objectives. The agents move towards the chosen exit.

Appendix A.11. Learning

Learning is not implemented in this model.

Appendix A.12. Prediction

Prediction is not implemented in this model.

Appendix A.13. Sensing

The pedestrian agents sense their neighboring pedestrians, obstacles and the group center of mass, evaluating their distance to the agent and, if applicable, calculate the acting social forces.

Appendix A.14. Interaction

The main interaction between agents is through the calculation of the social forces they apply to each other.

Appendix A.15. Stochasticity

The stochasticity is applied in this model in the processes of pedestrian and group spawning and exit choosing. The pedestrians are randomly clustered around their group centers (within a certain distance from the group center), which are randomly picked locations inside the open space polygon with uniform random distribution, the exits are chosen with weighted random distribution, where the weight the exit width.

Appendix A.16. Collectives

The collectives implemented in the model are the pedestrians' social groups. The social groups are modeled as entities, as they keep track of group members and the group centroid (calculated each cycle). The pedestrians will use the state variables of their group agents for the motion submodel.

Appendix A.17. Observation

The only observed variables during and after the model are the count of the current pedestrians in the model (the ones who did not egress at a given time step), and the number of pedestrians who left at each time step, which are calculated dynamically by counting the agents.

Appendix A.18. Initialization

The model is intended to simulate multiple environmental and behavioral scenarios. Each scenario is defined in an experiment, which in GAMA represents an execution of a model, being initialized with key values to represent the scenario. The environment is built from shapefiles containing relevant geometries. For a given open space, 3 files must be passed as parameters to parameters are *buildings_file*, *targets_file* and *start_area_file* which represent the shapefiles with the geometries of, respectively, the surrounding and internal buildings of the open space, the geometries representing the available exits and the area in which the pedestrians will spawn.

The building geometries come from the OpenStreetMap (OSM) initiative, a volunteer-based mapping project to map the entire world, offering the geographic data for free use. This data source was chosen due to its growing support, free-use data and wide and detailed coverage of accurate geographical data across the world. The exit and start area geometries are created manually with the QGIS software, using as reference the data from OSM.

nb_people is an initialization parameter representing the number of pedestrians that will spawn in the simulation. *group_size* represents the group size every group will have.

Based on the set value of these aforementioned parameters at the start of the simulations, the number of groups is calculated. At the beginning of a simulation, for each obtained group, a group center location is randomly created to guarantee a uniform distribution across the environment area. The pedestrians which are members of a specific group are then spawned with two-dimensional random uniform distribution within a set distance to the center of their respective groups. The group members are then assigned to their group agents, having mutual access to each other. Then, all members of a group choose the same exit, randomly distributed by the weight of the exit width (i.e., a wider exit is more likely to be chosen than a narrow one).

Appendix A.19. Input data

The model does not use input data to represent time-varying processes.

Appendix A.20. Submodels

The submodels in this model are implemented in the behavior of the pedestrian agents and group behavior. They consist on the (1) egress submodel and (2) group auxiliary submodel.

Appendix A.21. Egress submodel

This submodel describes the egress action of the pedestrians. They pursue the chosen exit for their group, moving through space until the desired exit is reached, avoiding strangers and obstacles, and maintaining group cohesion. The motion is implemented with adapted versions of the classic SFM by Helbing et. al [7], with an extension to adopt group behavior, presented by Moussaïd et al [15]. The implementations are inspired in the implementation in ¹², adapted for the GAMA platform.

The parameters of this model are presented in Table A.4. The parameters for the classic SFM were set based on the simulations made in the original study [7]. The parameters for the group SFM component were chosen based on multiple simulations, until group behavior provided more realism, through discussion followed by group consensus among the authors. This *expert-panel* approach was required due to the lack of empirical studies for high-density group behavior. Further calibration of these parameters should be done in future work.

For each simulation cycle, the submodel for each pedestrian agent acts as follows:

1. The heading is calculated through the current instant speed components, using the *atan2* operation. If both speed components have a non-zero value, the heading is the angle towards the chosen exit.

$$heading = atan2(speedY, speedX)$$

¹²[urlhttps://github.com/chraibi/SocialForceModel](https://github.com/chraibi/SocialForceModel)

Table A.4: Egress submodel parameters

Parameter	Description	Unit
V0	Desired walking speed of a pedestrian	m/s
A_ped	The pedestrian repulsion strength parameter of the classic SFM	-
D_ped	The pedestrian range of repulsive forces parameter of the classic SFM	m
A_obs	The obstacle repulsion strength parameter of the classic SFM	-
D_obs	The obstacle range of repulsive forces parameter of the classic SFM	m
ped_influence_radius	The range within which a pedestrian exerts social forces	m
obs_influence_radius	The range within which an obstacle exerts social forces	m
Tr	The relaxation parameter of the classic SFM	s
shoulder_length	The shoulder width of the pedestrians	m
B_group_attr	The intra-group attraction strength parameter of the extended group SFM	-
B_group_rep	The intra-group repulsion strength parameter of the extended group SFM	-
group_rep_threshold	The range within which group members exert repulsive forces	m
group_attr_threshold	The distance from group center from which attractive forces occur	m

Else, the heading is calculated through the direction vector between the pedestrian agent's location and the centroid of its desired exit using the $heading(from, to)$ operation, where $from$ is a location from where the heading points, and to , where the heading points to:

$$heading(from, to) = atan2(to.y - from.y, to.x - from.x)$$

In steps 2,3,and 4, all the forces acting upon the pedestrian will be calculated. The X and Y components of the forces are summed in variables sum_forces_X and sum_forces_Y , respectively.

- The pedestrian agent obtains its group's centroid from the respective entity. Using the centroid, if the agent's distance to the centroid is more than the defined group attraction threshold, the pedestrian calculates the group cohesion force components using the following equations:

$$groupAttrForceX = B_group_attr \times \cos(heading(self, centroid)) \times (1 - \sin(heading(self, centroid) - heading))$$

$$groupAttrForceY = B_group_attr \times \sin(heading(self, centroid)) \times (1 - \sin(heading(self, centroid) - heading))$$

- The pedestrian queries its neighbours, considering the influence radius, and for each one : If the neighbor pedestrian is a member of its group, and the distance between the agent and the neighbors is less that the group repulsion threshold, the group collision avoidance forces are calculated using the equation:

$$groupRepForceX = B_group_rep \times \cos(heading(neighbor, self)) \times (1 - \sin(heading(neighbor, self) - heading))$$

$$groupRepForceY = B_group_rep \times \sin(heading(neighbor, self)) \times (1 - \sin(heading(neighbor, self) - heading))$$

Else, if a neighbor pedestrian is not part of the agent's group, the repulsive forces from the classic SFM are calculated with the equations:

$$pedRepForceX = A_ped \times e^{(shoulder_length - distance(self, obstacle)) / D_ped} \times \cos(heading(neighbor, self)) \times (1 - \sin(heading(neighbor, self) - heading))$$

$$pedRepForceY = A_ped \times e^{(shoulder_length - distance(self, obstacle)) / D_ped} \times \sin(heading(neighbor, self)) \times (1 - \sin(heading(neighbor, self) - heading))$$

4. The repulsive force components from the neighboring obstacles within the obstacle influence radius are calculated, using the equations:

$$obsRepForceX = A_obs \times e^{(shoulder_length - distance(self, obstacle)) / D_ped} \times \cos(heading(obstacle, self)) \times (1 - \sin(heading(obstacle, self) - heading))$$

$$obsRepForceY = A_obs \times e^{(shoulder_length - distance(self, obstacle)) / D_ped} \times \sin(heading(obstacle, self)) \times (1 - \sin(heading(obstacle, self) - heading))$$

5. Having the total sums of the X and Y force components, the instantaneous speed components are calculated as follows:

$$speedX = speedX + step \times (sum_forces_x + (V0 \times \cos(hd) - speedX) / Tr)$$

$$speedY = speedY + step \times (sum_forces_y + (V0 \times \sin(hd) - speedY) / Tr)$$

6. Having the speed components, the pedestrian tries to move, obtaining its next location:

$$next_location = (location.x + speedX \times step, location.y + speedY \times step)$$

If the next position is a valid position, the agent's position is set as that position. Else, the agent does not move, and both speed components are set to 0. If the next position is inside the agent's desired exit, it is removed from the simulation, else, the submodel repeats for the agent.

Appendix A.22. Group submodel

This submodel consists in updating the group characteristics each cycle, according to the locations and behaviors of pedestrians. After the group and pedestrian initialization, at each cycle, a group agent behaves as follows:

1. The group agent checks if a group member has left the simulation. If that happens, it is removed from group's list of members.
2. The agent calculates the group's centroid based on the current position of all its current members.
3. If there are no members left, the group agent is removed from the simulation. Else, return to step 1.